

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Silver(I) Ion Catalysed Oxidation of Propionic Acid by Peroxodisulphate Ion

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Manuscript received 18 February 1977, revised, 22 August 1977, accepted 21 November 1977

Kinetics of Ag(I)-catalysed oxidation of propionic acid by peroxodisulphate have been studied. The rate is first order in peroxodisulphate and silver(I). A complex formation between Ag^+ and propionic acid (P. A.) is indicated. The following rate law holds :

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \left\{ k_1 + \frac{k_2[\text{Ag}^+]_T}{(1+K[\text{PA}])} \right\}$$

The values of k_1 and k_2 were found to be $0.30 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $0.21 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ respectively at 60° .

PEROXODISULPHATE oxidations of several organic and inorganic substrates both under catalysed and uncatalysed conditions have been a field of interest for several group of workers¹⁻². Among the monocarboxylic acids, oxidations of formate³ and the acetate⁴ ions by peroxodisulphate have been studied, but the oxidation of propionic acid remains uninvestigated.

Experimental

Potassium peroxodisulphate, silver sulphate, propionic acid and other chemicals (E. Merck, G.R.) were always prepared fresh in doubly distilled water and standardized by usual methods.

A kinetic run was initiated by adding the required volume of peroxodisulphate solution into the reaction vessel containing the requisite amounts of propionic acid and silver sulphate solutions kept at a desired temperature in a thermostat within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The progress of the reaction was studied by estimating residual peroxodisulphate iodometrically⁵ at different intervals of time.

Results

Stoichiometry and Reaction products :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined with known excess of potassium peroxodisulphate (0.04 M) over propionic acid at two different concentrations (0.002 M and 0.004 M) under identical conditions. The excess peroxodisulphate was determined iodometrically⁵. It was found that two moles of peroxodisulphate are consumed per mole of the acid.

The main reaction products were acetaldehyde and carbon dioxide. Acetaldehyde was identified in the reaction mixture by spot test⁶ and its conver-

sion into 2 : 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative which was subsequently identified by its m.p.

Rate Measurements :

Preliminary experiments showed that the reaction proceeds with a measurable rate above 50° with 0.02M reactant concentrations and $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ Ag^+ concentration. Peroxodisulphate follows a first order disappearance at all the concentrations. Hence the values of 'k' given in the following tables have been obtained from the slopes of the linear first order plots between $\log [a-x]$ vs. time.

(a) Peroxodisulphate dependence :

The variation of the rate over a ten fold range of initial $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ concentrations was studied. The values of the rate constants obtained from the first-order linear plots at different $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ concentrations are tabulated below :

	1	2	3	4	5	
$k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1} =$	1.19	1.17	1.15	1.17	1.28	1.28

Evidently, the order of the reaction which respect to peroxodisulphate is one.

(b) Propionic acid dependence :

The rate constants corresponding to different initial concentrations of propionic acid are summarized in Table 2.

	1	2	3	4	5	
$k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1} =$	1.40	1.36	1.15	1.02	1.02	0.98

Table 2 shows that the rate constants tend to decrease with increasing concentrations of propionic acid. It appears that the rate is independent of the concentration of propionic acid and the decreasing trend of the rate constants may be ascribed to a decrease of concentration of Ag(I) owing to a complex formation of Ag(I) and propionic acid.

(c) Silver ion concentration dependence :

The Ag(I) concentration was varied in the range $(2-10) \times 10^{-4} M$ and the results are given in Table 3.

TABLE-3 SILVER(I) DEPENDENCE

[Potassium peroxodisulphate]=0.02M, [Propionic acid]=0.02M, Temperature=60°					
[Ag ⁺] $\times 10^4 M$	=2	4	6	8	10
$k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	=0.75	1.15	1.62	1.92	2.41

Plot of k against silver ion concentration gives a linear relationship. Computation of the data of the above table shows that the observed rate constant satisfies the equation :

$$k = k' + k''[\text{Ag}^+]$$

where k' and k'' are the rate constants for the uncatalysed and catalysed pathways respectively with values $0.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $0.21 M^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, obtained from the intercept and slope of the linear plot.

The decrease of the rate constant with the increase of propionic acid concentration could be due to a complex formation of Ag(I) and the organic acid. This necessitated further investigations. Evidence for the adduct formation of propionic acid with Ag(I) was obtained from the rate constant - Ag(I) concentration plots obtained with varying concentrations of propionic acid at different concentrations of Ag(I). The rate data at three different acid concentrations (0.01M, 0.02M, 0.03 M) satisfy the equations :

$$\begin{aligned} k &= 0.30 \times 10^{-4} + 0.25[\text{Ag}^+] \text{ sec}^{-1} & \dots & \text{(I)} \\ k &= 0.30 \times 10^{-4} + 0.21[\text{Ag}^+] \text{ sec}^{-1} & \dots & \text{(II)} \\ k &= 0.30 \times 10^{-4} + 0.18[\text{Ag}^+] \text{ sec}^{-1} & \dots & \text{(III)} \end{aligned}$$

In each case different values of k'' but the same value of k' is obtained.

The effect of hydrogen ion was studied by varying perchloric acid in the concentration range (0.01-0.06) M and there is almost no effect. Allyl acetate decreased the rate, but no limiting rate was obtained.

Mechanism :

The catalytic activity of silver ion is due to the formation of higher valent silver species. The nature of these species (Ag(II) and Ag(III)) has been

discussed by Anderson and Kochi⁷. Recent evidences point to the existence of Ag(II) in aqueous acid solution which is in accordance with the observation of Higginson and Marshall⁸.

The various rate dependences in the present reaction lead to the following mechanism :

If Ag^+ and not the Ag^I complex is reactive, following rate law would be obtained :

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] + k_2[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}][\text{Ag}^+]_{\text{free}} \dots (6)$$

$$\text{or } k = k_1 + k_2[\text{Ag}^+]_{\text{free}} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$= k_1 + \frac{k_2[\text{Ag}^+]_{\text{T}}}{(1 + K[\text{P.A.]})} \quad \dots (8)$$

where $[\text{Ag}^+]_{\text{free}}$ and $[\text{Ag}^+]_{\text{T}}$ are the concentrations of free silver ion and total Ag(I). Equation (8) at constant P.A. would reduce to (9).

$$k = k_1 + k''[\text{Ag}^+]_{\text{T}} \quad \dots (9)$$

where k_1 is identical with k' . An average value of K was found to be $24 M^{-1}$. The second order rate constant was calculated to be $0.21 M^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$.

Acknowledgement

We thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of us (S.P.M.).

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